

MANUFACTURE AND EVALUATION OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

A composite consisting of aluminium-5 wt.% copper alloy and continuous pitch-based carbon fibres has been fabricated by liquid metal infiltration. The composite was well infiltrated with no evidence of deleterious reaction products at the fibre/matrix interface. The bond between fibre and matrix was good, as evidenced by a Young's modulus which matched 'Rule of Mixtures' predictions. Heat-treated composite (solutionised and artificially aged to produce maximum matrix hardness) had a modulus of 240 GPa in the longitudinal direction and ~30 GPa transverse to the fibres. The composite failed at a strength of 350 MPa and a strain of 0.15 %, compared with 420 MPa and 0.21 % for composite in the as-cast condition. Transverse strength was, however, increased by the heat treatment, from 40 MPa to 60 MPa.

INTRODUCTION

Most work carried out on metal matrix composites has focused upon particle-reinforced materials despite the fact that continuous-fibre composites offer, potentially, the greatest gains in specific properties. The problem with fibres is incorporating them into the metal matrix without introducing mechanical and/or chemical damage to impair their effectiveness as a reinforcement. Nonetheless, recent studies have shown that well-consolidated fibre composites can be fabricated without serious fibre degradation by using the method of liquid metal infiltration (LMI), as illustrated in a report [1] on the manufacture of a composite consisting of 6061 aluminium alloy reinforced with alumina ("Altex") fibres. Here, it was evident that no deleterious chemical reaction products had formed between fibre and matrix and that a strong interface bond was established which gave a Young's modulus matching 'Rule of Mixtures' predictions. However, notwithstanding the good specific properties of 6061/Altex composite, the relatively high density of alumina (3.3 gcm^{-3} compared with 2.7 gcm^{-3} for aluminium) provides a limit to achievable properties. Hence a logical way forward is to use carbon fibres for the reinforcement because of their lower density (2 gcm^{-3}) and higher modulus, ~400 GPa compared with ~200-300 GPa for alumina fibres.

Attempts have been previously made to use carbon fibres for reinforcing aluminium alloy but the results were unsuccessful because of poor infiltration of the fibre preform and extensive chemical reaction between fibre and matrix [2]. The present work, whilst adopting a similar infiltration

technique, utilises apparatus with improved control of processing parameters to enhance infiltration and minimise the extent of any interfacial reaction. The use of a heat-treatable aluminium-copper alloy for the matrix is also described.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURE

Nominal aluminium-5 wt.% copper alloy was used for the matrix. The reinforcement was continuous, pitch-based carbon fibre (Amoco P55) of $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$ diameter which was supplied on a bobbin with ~ 1000 filaments per tow.

The preform was made by winding the fibres onto a steel plate to a thickness of ~ 10 mm. It was heated at $\sim 600^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 minutes and transferred to a preheated (450°C) die. Liquid aluminium alloy at $\sim 850^\circ\text{C}$ was then introduced and a hydraulic pressure of a few MPa applied to infiltrate the preform. After a few seconds, when infiltration was complete, a higher pressure (~ 25 MPa) was applied to assist consolidation. The die was then cooled to $\sim 300^\circ\text{C}$, the pressure was removed and at $\sim 100^\circ\text{C}$ the composite was extracted from the die by means of a dovetail profile on the ram. A sample of unreinforced alloy was processed by the same LMI route for comparison studies.

AGEING EXPERIMENTS

Samples of composite and unreinforced alloy, 10 mm x 10 mm x 10 mm, were solution treated at 530°C for 18 hrs and immediately quenched into water at $\sim 80^\circ\text{C}$. They were then artificially aged at 170°C for periods of up to 120 hours.

Specimens were mounted in cold-cure resin and surface ground using progressively finer grades of abrasive, finishing with colloidal silica compound. Microhardness measurements were made on polished specimens using a Leco M400 with a Vickers diamond indenter. Ten indentations were made per specimen employing a load of 25 gf and a dwell time of 20 seconds.

MICROSTRUCTURAL EXAMINATION

Polished specimens were examined by light microscopy (LM) followed by chemical analysis using electron-probe microanalysis (EPMA) in the scanning electron microscope (SEM). Fracture surfaces of tested specimens were also examined in the SEM.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed on thin (~ 100 nm) sections prepared by grinding 3 mm diameter discs to $\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$ thickness, with final thinning accomplished by atom milling using a cryogenic stage to avoid overageing. Composite and unreinforced alloy in the cast and peak-aged conditions were studied using this technique.

MECHANICAL TESTS

Tensile tests were carried out on an Instron 1195 machine using a cross-head speed of 1.0 mm per minute, a minimum of five specimens being tested per condition. The specimens were parallel sided with a gauge length of 30 mm and a cross-section of 6 mm x 3 mm. Soft aluminium end tabs were applied to minimise grip damage during testing [3].

RESULTS

MICROSTRUCTURE

Unreinforced Alloy

The as-cast alloy had a typical dendritic structure, with grains $\sim 150 \mu\text{m}$ diameter, extensive coring of copper, and fairly coarse grain-boundary particles. After solution treatment, the degree of coring and the amount of second phase were substantially reduced. The average microhardness was 90 HV. Upon artificial ageing at 170°C , the microhardness increased with time, Fig. 1, to reach a peak of 140 HV after 24 hours treatment. TEM examination of a specimen in the peak-hardness condition showed a high density of oriented plate-like precipitates, $\sim 50 \text{ nm}$ in diameter, Fig. 2. Diffraction analysis indicated that the precipitate was θ' , a tetragonal phase with $a = 0.40 \text{ nm}$ and $c = 0.58 \text{ nm}$, lying on $\{100\}$ planes of the aluminium lattice.

As-Cast Composite

A metallographic section, Fig. 3a, showed that the composite was well consolidated, with an even distribution of fibres of volume fraction 0.55 ± 0.05 and a matrix porosity less than 1.0 %. There is no evidence here of a chemical reaction between the fibre and matrix. The matrix had a smaller grain size ($\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ diameter) than unreinforced alloy with, again, grain-boundary phases and evidence of coring. TEM examination confirmed that the fibre/matrix interface was, essentially, free from reaction product, Fig. 3b. The fibre is seen to consist of fine, $\sim 10 \text{ nm}$ diameter crystals, which diffraction analysis indicated were hexagonal phase, $a = 0.25 \text{ nm}$ and $c = 0.68 \text{ nm}$, with a pronounced $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle$ texture [4]. Dislocations in the matrix, Fig. 3c, appeared to extend from fibre to fibre.

Heat-Treated Composite

After solution treatment, the amount of matrix second phase was reduced and coring was removed. The average microhardness of the matrix was 95 HV and, upon ageing at 170°C , it increased with time to reach a maximum of 135 HV after ~ 24 hours, Fig. 1; note that the composite over-aged more quickly than unreinforced alloy. TEM examination of peak-hardness material showed the same high density of θ' precipitates as found in peak-hardness alloy, although the dislocations which characterised as-cast composite were hard to find. Again there was no evidence of an interface reaction between fibre and matrix.

MECHANICAL TESTS

Unreinforced Alloy

Stress-strain curves from as-cast and from heat-treated alloy are shown in Fig. 4. From the initial, linear region of the curves, Young's modulus was estimated to be 70 GPa. Yield stress for as-cast metal was 20 MPa, the tensile strength was 185 MPa and the strain to failure was 9.5 %. After heat treatment, the corresponding values were 210 MPa, 325 MPa and 4.5 %. Averaged data with standard deviations are given in Table 1.

Composite, Longitudinal

Stress-strain curves for as-cast and heat-treated composite are given in Fig. 5. The plots are, essentially, linear and have gradients of 200 GPa and 240 GPa respectively. The corresponding tensile strengths were 420 MPa and 350 MPa, with strains to failure of 0.21 % and 0.15 %. Collated data are given in Table 1.

The fracture surface of as-cast composite, Fig. 6a, showed little sign of de-bonding or of fibre pull-out. The appearance of exposed fibre, due to local matrix deformation, confirmed the absence of interface reaction product whilst the morphology of the fibre fracture appeared to be consistent with its $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle$ texture. The fracture surface of heat-treated composite, Fig. 6b, showed similar features, apart from there being less exposed fibre surface.

Composite, Transverse

Stress-strain curves for as-cast and heat-treated composite are shown in Fig. 7. The gradient of the linear region of each curve was 30 GPa. Only the as-cast composite shows an identifiable yield point and this occurred at a stress of 30 MPa. The respective tensile strengths were 40 MPa and 60 MPa, with failure strains of 0.18 % and 0.20 %. Collated data are given in Table 1.

The fracture surface of as-cast composite, Fig. 8a, showed exposed fibres and deformed metal, intermetallic phases being revealed where fibres have separated from matrix. There was some evidence of fibre splitting, moreso in the heat-treated composite, Fig. 8b; note also the absence of intermetallic phases in interface regions of heat-treated composite.

DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURAL EVALUATION

The method of liquid metal infiltration produced a well-consolidated composite with low matrix porosity and an even distribution of carbon fibres, ~0.55 volume fraction. The presence of fibres had limited the growth of metal grains during composite fabrication, as shown by the larger grain size of unreinforced alloy subjected to the same casting conditions, but there was no sign of any chemical reaction between the fibre and metal matrix. The level of coring within the metal and the appreciable amount of interdendritic CuAl_2 phase present was to be expected with the casting process adopted here. The high dislocation density found in the matrix was a result of the strains developed by differential thermal contraction ($\sim 25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) between fibre and matrix during composite manufacture. The strain thus produced (~1 %) is well in excess of the yield strain for the alloy (0.03 %, see Fig. 4) and consequently causes plastic flow, that is the generation and movement of dislocations.

Solution treatment of the composite at 530°C for 18 hrs, followed by quenching into hot water, decreased substantially the amount of interdendritic CuAl_2 phase and matrix coring. Artificial ageing at 170°C produced a matrix peak hardness of 135 HV after 24 hours, a similar treatment to that required to achieve peak-hardness in unreinforced alloy. These post-infiltration thermal treatments did not, however, appear to encourage any fibre/matrix interface reaction. The age-hardening response was associated with the formation of θ' precipitates [5] although the initial ageing response and the over-ageing characteristics were more rapid in the composite than in unreinforced alloy. The differences are attributed to θ' precipitates forming directly on the numerous dislocations in the composite and by-passing the GP zones.

MECHANICAL EVALUATION

The efficacy of the fibre reinforcement will be evaluated by comparing theoretical predictions with experimental data, starting with elastic properties and continuing with yielding behaviour.

Consider first the ideal situation where the fibres are uniformly distributed and the composite is well consolidated with a good fibre/matrix bond. We may then predict a value for Young's modulus in the fibre direction, E_1 , using the 'Rule of Mixtures' (ROM)

$$E_1 = E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f), \quad (1)$$

where E_f and E_m are Young's modulus of fibre and matrix respectively, and V_f is the fibre volume fraction. Substituting our experimental value of 70 GPa for E_m , the manufacturer's figure of ~380 GPa for E_f , and 0.55 for V_f , then gives a value of 240 GPa for E_1 .

This value of Young's modulus is significantly higher than that indicated by the gradient of the stress-strain curve for as-cast composite (200 GPa, see Table 1) and there are a number of factors which may have subscribed to the difference. Firstly, an ineffective fibre/matrix bond may have been responsible, but this can be discounted in view of the fracture characteristics exhibited by the composite, see Fig. 6a. Secondly, the fibre modulus may be lower than the manufacturer's value used in the calculation. This also is unlikely since the gradient of the stress-strain curve for heat-treated composite was 240 GPa, higher than that of as-cast composite and in excellent agreement with ROM predictions. If we now consider previous stress-strain results on continuous fibre composites [6], these usually exhibited a marked reduction in gradient, an effect which was absent in present studies. The effect is referred to as a 'knee point' and is associated with matrix yield, as confirmed by slip-line observations [7]. It is our contention that, since the matrix of as-cast composite was already in a stressed (~20 MPa) and yielded condition, as demonstrated by the above dislocation studies, the composite stress-strain characteristics were related only to the fibre contributions. Indeed, the value of 210 GPa for $E_f V_f$ is in good agreement with the experimental figure of 200 GPa. Hence in the heat-treated composite, it must be presumed that the matrix behaved elastically up to the point of failure of the composite and did not reach its yield point. This is not surprising since the failure strain of heat-treated composite, 0.15 % from Fig. 5, was much lower than the yield strain of heat-treated alloy, 0.25 % from Fig. 4. These ideas, showing the relationships between fibre and matrix contributions, are illustrated schematically in Fig. 9, including 'knee points' on projected stress-strain curves.

With regard to failure of the composite, the lower strength achieved after heat treatment, 350 MPa compared with 420 MPa, is attributed to the lower damage tolerance of the heat-treated matrix.

For transverse properties of the composite, the following ROM expression is available for predicting the modulus, E_2 :

$$1/E_2 = (1 - V_f)/E_m + V_f/E_f \quad (2)$$

Data on the transverse properties of this grade of carbon fibre are, however, not available and so we choose instead to deduce the radial stiffness of the fibre from equation (2) using our experimentally derived value for E_2 . Hence, substituting 30 GPa for E_2 and 70 GPa for E_m , gives a radial stiffness of 20 GPa. This figure is indicative of an anisotropy factor of ~20 for P55 carbon fibre, not unreasonable when comparing the fibre with single-crystal graphite which has an anisotropy factor of 28 (*i.e.* 950 GPa perpendicular and 34 GPa parallel to the c-axis).

The yield behaviour of transverse composites (see Fig. 7) resembled that of unreinforced alloy because in this loading orientation the fibres behaved as discontinuous reinforcements and could not support any residual tensile stress in the matrix. The higher yield stress (as-cast, 30 MPa) compared with unreinforced alloy (as-cast, 20 MPa) is believed to be associated with compressive residual stresses in the matrix which act in opposition to the applied load [6].

Considering the tensile strength of transverse composites, both as-cast and heat-treated materials had values lower than unreinforced alloy. This is attributed to the high strains in the fibre which, because of the low fibre modulus, resulted from relatively low stresses. Fracture of the composite then occurred because the fibre/matrix bond was unable to sustain the strain.

Finally, the present results demonstrate that, whilst the incorporation of unidirectional carbon fibres into aluminium alloy confers high stiffness and strength in a direction parallel to the fibres, they lead to transverse properties which are inferior to those of unreinforced alloy. Clearly, if a more isotropic performance is required, a complex fibre arrangement would have to be considered, such as a cross-ply array.

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Table 1. Tensile test data

material	condition	modulus GPa	yield stress MPa	strength MPa	failure strain %
alloy	as-cast	70 ± 5	20 ± 3	185 ± 5	9.5 ± 0.5
	heat-treated	70 ± 5	210 ± 10	325 ± 10	4.5 ± 0.5
composite longitudinal	as-cast	200 ± 15	-----	420 ± 25	0.21 ± 0.03
	heat-treated	240 ± 10	not achieved	350 ± 20	0.15 ± 0.02
composite transverse	as-cast	30 ± 5	30 ± 5	40 ± 10	0.18 ± 0.03
	heat-treated	30 ± 5	not achieved	60 ± 10	0.20 ± 0.03

Figure 1. Microhardness vs ageing at 170°C, unreinforced alloy and composite matrix.

Figure 2. Heat-treated alloy with matrix precipitates, TEM.

Figure 3. As-cast composite, (a) transverse section, LM, (b) fibre/matrix interface and (c) matrix dislocations, TEM.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves, alloy

Figure 5. Stress-strain curves, longitudinal composite.

Figure 6. Fracture surface, longitudinal composite, (a) as-cast and (b) heat-treated, SEM.

Figure 7. Stress-strain curves, transverse composite.

Figure 8. Fracture, transverse composite, (a) as-cast, (b) heat-treated, SEM.

Figure 9. Schematic showing fibre and matrix contributions to stress-strain behaviour.